

A PARTICIPATORY META DATA (WEB) CATALOGUE FOR DATA SHARING

ARE YOU CURIOUS WHAT IS INSIDE
THIS TREASURE CHEST?

METADATA, that includes:

- links to, and information about the datasets and
- mechanisms for improvement of metadata through a participatory approach through 'Edit on Git'* as well as
- searching tools

*Edit the Git: see how does it work and how to operate, and the tutorials

HOW CAN IT BE ACCESSED?
<https://catalogue.ejpsoil.eu>

GOOD TO KNOW:

Metadata records are stored in a convenient MCF format, a metadata convention from the geopython community, which is a compatible subset of ISO19115. If you prefer a guided editor, consider to modify the record using mdme

AUTHORS

EJP SOIL Workpackage 6
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A sustainable tool

The catalogue provides an overview and allows better findability of relevant authoritative and research soil datasets that can be used by the Mission Soil, the Mission Soil projects, other soil research projects, single researchers and by local, regional, national and European authorities. There are no restrictions on access to the metadata and it is therefore of value to the entire EU soil community and adjacent domains. The EJP SOIL catalogue will be transferred in 2025 to the European Soil Observatory.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

The catalogue's unique benefit lies in its ability to incorporate metadata from soil datasets stored in major repositories across Europe, such as ZENODO, Cordis, national repositories, ESDAC, and the INSPIRE data portal if chosen by administrators.

This enhances the speed and effectiveness of searches for users within Europe. As such it complements major metadata catalogs like ISRIC, ESDAC, and GSP, focusing specifically on soil data in Europe. Following the completion of the EJP SOIL program in January 2025, the metadata content and software will be made available for reuse to ESDAC/EUSO.

To support EU Mission Soils knowledge and data repository, the project SoilWise will take over the catalogue content and software and continue its enrichment with metadata, also on non-geographical data and knowledge sources.

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply.

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ scientists, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL WP6 – FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME

The objective of the work package is the development of an agreed knowledge base and database to improve the European contribution towards international reporting on soils, and the accuracy of European agricultural policies.

TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Supporting harmonized European soil information, including for international reporting

Mission SOIL: Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:
EJP SOIL catalogue

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

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